

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EMEH****FIRST NAME: KELECHI****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma/Cleenewerck**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

TECHNIQUES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The period covered writing skills and techniques that are vital for effective academic writing. This is really useful as a starting point because it enables students reflect on the journey ahead and some of the requirements in writing academic papers. According to EUCLID, an academic essay is geared towards aims to encouraging readers to appreciate and learn about an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2). The lessons of period one is basically the foundation for any effective academic writing.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING

Since inception of literacy and academic writing, there have been varied options of writing by different scholars. In this period one, the course was designed to purposefully outline the various styles and techniques required in writing academic papers. In other words, I learnt about the rules of the thumb in writing academic papers. Some of these rules are essential for other writings. It is note-worthy to mention that I have known some of these rules at the fringes, but the course pack has helped to refresh the memory while inculcating useful knowledge. Just like in real life scenarios, structures built on strong foundation usually are stronger and durable.

Of important interest are the instructive advice that accompanied some of the rules. I found some of the rules were basic while others demonstrated advanced use of English Language. It was quite educative to understand the fundamentals of writing an essay which include write clearly, write short and medium sentences, staying focused and

aligned to the topic, use of connectors and prepositions. (EUCLID 2015, 43). There are many aspects of writing a good essay which would be explored in this paper. The aim of this response paper is to deepen the understanding of period one.

a) Styles

The drafting of academic paper usually either the American or British style of writing. Each of the styles have distinct spelling, referencing, and sometimes structural patterns. It is worthy to note that both styles should not be used at the same paper (EUCLID 2015, 55). Technically, this could be a little challenging since most of the differences between both styles are not well known. However, I will always endeavor to cross-check the appropriate sources.

Furthermore, there is another distinction between personal and academic writing. Based on the focus on this response paper, I decided to highlight other forms of styles that could be found in both American and British styles.

b) Plagiarism

This is another important element in academic writing. According to EUCLID course pack, plagiarism is frowned upon as a technique in writing academic paper.

“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author” (EUCLID 2015, 9).

This means that students should ensure that proper give credit to the source of information used during academic writing. However, there is a gap in the meaning of plagiarism. In some instances, students could use incorrect citation while writing papers. Would this be regarded as plagiarism?

i) *Common Mistakes in Grammar*

This is another rule of the thumb that is very vital. The importance of punctuation and use of appropriate pronouns cannot be over emphasized. The understanding of proper grammar is one of the vital techniques for affective academic writing. The use of comma, full stop, semi-colon and other punctuation marks are necessary for the better communication and meaning to the academic text. However, this is one of the most challenging aspects of a good academic writing. It is clearly expected that students not to use abbreviations, write acronyms in full and consult the dictionary if in doubt of the grammar (EUCLID 2015, 49).

Coupled with the above points is the fact that use of ambiguity is equally unacceptable as a technique in academic writing. Ambiguity could be in the form of using flowering words, jargons, buzz words or just simply uncommon words.

In addition, there were other crucial information highlighted in the period which illustrates precisely the common grammatical errors. For example, the misrepresentation of possessive pronoun and contraction meaning of a pronoun. Equally, the use of adjectives and adverbs were elaborated in the material for period one. I really found interesting that the period revolved mainly around basic instructions in English language.

ii) *Referencing*

This is an important writing technique which is essential for academic writing. In period one under review, the student was meant to comprehend the various forms of referencing. Parenthetical referencing necessitates the student to use in-text referencing while the footnote referencing allows the student to use detailed reference at the bottom of the page.

Further to the above point, it is also important to note the emphasis on using Turabian style of referencing for academic writing in EUCLID.

3) **CONCLUSION**

This period one is an educative introduction to the doctorate programme and sets the foundation of the academic course. As I earlier mentioned, a strong foundation ensure that any structure would be durable and sustainable. I have rigorously been exposed to the techniques of writing academic paper which sets out the standards as well as the expectations. EUCLILD prefers the use of American English, however other international versions are recognized and acceptable. Several academic writers do not adopt/ discuss writing style guide, because of the believe that each writing should follow a standard English writing style which demonstrates the innate quality for any writer. This is not usually factual as a style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output (EUCLID 2015, 52). As students, a vital addition to the course content would be to also highlight the need for publication in scientific journals. Most of the journals have specific writing patterns which require strict adhere. This means that students need to be exposed to various international writing style guides.

Personally, the reality would be to keep practicing using the acquired skills and to be better acquainted with the components. The foundational bricks have been put into perspective; it is anticipated that subsequent periods would build upon the structure.

REFERENCES

EUCLID University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.